

THE COMPOSITION OF THE FATTY ACIDS OF THE SEED FAT OF *LOPHIRA ALATA* (OCHNACEÆ)

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The mixed fatty acids of the oil from the seeds of *Lophira alata* (Ochnaceæ) have been separated by the usual methods into solid (41.9%) and liquid acids (58.1%). The fatty acids have been calculated to be palmitic (23.2%), stearic (0.3%), arachidic (4.8%), behenic (4.9%), lignoceric (6.9%), palmitoleic (11.7%), oleic (8.3%), linoleic (31.5%), eicosenoic (2.1%), docosenoic (5.6%) and unsaponifiable matter (0.7%).

The fat is obtained from the decorticated seeds of *Lophira alata* (Ochnaceæ). The tree is not indigenous to India but found extensively in tropical Africa from where the present sample was procured. The tree amongst others supplies the so-called African oak. The fat from the seeds of this tree is sometimes called Niam fat (Schweinfurth, *Botan. Ergeb. der ersten Niam-Niam Reise*; *Bull. Imp. Inst.*, 1909, 7, 367). It is also called Meni oil in Sierra Leone and Zawa oil in Egyptian Sudan. Natives in certain localities in tropical Africa (Heckel, *Les Graines grasses nouvelles ou peu connues des colonies francaises*, Paris, 1861) use it for culinary purposes and also as a hair oil. The oil has also been suggested as suitable for soap-making and the residual oil cake as suitable for fertiliser (Anon., *Bull. Imp. Inst.*, 1935, 33, 286).

A number of workers have recorded constants for this oil. Thus according to Lewkowitsch (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1907, 1265) the oil has the following characteristics. Specific gravity at 40°, 0.9016-0.9044; S.V., 182-195; I.V., 70-72.5; R.M.V., 0.8-0.9; unsaponifiable 0.5-9.0%; Titer, 47° to 49°.

The seeds from Sierra Leone, Sudan and Uganda have been examined by the Imperial Institute, London (Anon., *Bull. Imp. Inst.*, 1908, 6, 243, 366; 1912, 10, 226; 1935, 33, 284). The data of the fat from different localities are compared with those of ours in the table given below.

Characteristics.	Present sample.	Sierra Leone.	Sudan.	Uganda.
Sp. gr. 100/15°	—	0.859	—	0.8604
Sp. gr. 40/40°	0.9021	0.9016-0.9105	0.9063	—
M. p. (open tube)	27.0°	—	—	24.5°
Ref. Index at 40°	—	—	—	1.4610
Acid value	—	18.54-48.0	5.78	7.0
Sap. value	191.6	180.7-195.6	190.1	187.9
Iod. value (Wij's)	73.4	—	—	73.2
Iod. value (Hübl)	—	68.0-72.5	78.12	—
Unsaponifiable	0.7	0.5-2.5	1.38	1.3
Titer	—	45.0-49.0°	42.5°	43.8°
R.M.V.	0.7	—	—	—

The constants of the present sample therefore do not materially differ from those of the previous workers. Pickles and Hayworth (*Analyst*, 1911, 36, 493) have gone further into the question and besides the usual characteristics, which also do not materially differ from those of ours, investigated the fat by semi-quantitative methods. Thus they have separated the solid and liquid acids by lead salt-ether method and found that the saturated (solid) acids and unsaturated (liquid) acids are present in equal proportions. They have further subjected the solid acids to fractional crystallisation from alcohol and isolated and identified arachidic and palmitic acids though no quantitative data regarding these two acids have been given. There were indications that besides these two acids other components are present in the solid acids. The liquid acids had an iodine value of 139. They have identified linoleic and oleic acids in the liquid acids and on the basis of iodine value conclude that these two acids are present in

about equal proportions. They have not stated how they have estimated these two acids in presence of one another.

In the present work, following the Twitchell method of lead salt separation as modified by Hilditch (Hilditch, "The Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats," 1941, reprinted, p. 371) it has been found that the saturated (solid) and unsaturated (liquid) acids are 41.9 and 58.1 per cent respectively. The iodine value (3.81) of the saturated (solid) acids esters shows that the separation of the saturated from the unsaturated fatty acids is fairly good. In view of the absence of the iodine value data of the solid acids of Pickles and Hayworth it is not possible to judge the extent of the separation of the saturated from the unsaturated acids but it must be presumed, in view of the method available at that time (1911), that separation had not been complete and considerable quantity of certain unsaturated acid or acids has passed into the solid acids. This might explain the reason why equal proportion of solid and liquid acids was obtained.

So far as the liquid acids of Pickles and Hayworth were concerned, they stated, basing their argument on the iodine value (139), that oleic and linoleic acids occurred in equal proportions. This is a fallacy and as such cannot be admitted. It presupposes that oleic and linoleic acids are the only constituents of the liquid acids and that no other acid or acids are present in the liquid acids. This has, however, not been shown. If, on the other hand, certain unsaturated acids pass into the solid acids and certain amount of saturated acid^s passes into the liquid acids of which there is ample evidence, there may be more than one way of building up an iodine value of 139. The average molecular weights or in other words the saponification equivalents of solid and liquid acids are of prime importance in coming to any conclusion. The present investigation fully corroborates that C₁₆ mono-ethenoid (palmitoleic) is one of the major components of the liquid acids. The work confirms the presence of palmitic (23.2%) and arachidic (4.8%) acids as saturated fatty acids and oleic (8.3%) and linoleic (31.5%) as unsaturated fatty acids in this fat. Besides, by systematic fractionation of the methyl esters of the solid and liquid acids separately through 'E.H.P. Column' as employed by Hilditch *et al* (*loc. cit.*) and determination of S.E. and I.V. of various fractions, the following acids have been calculated in addition to those already stated: (1) stearic (0.3%), (2) behenic (4.9%), (3) lignoceric (6.9%), (4) palmitoleic (11.7%), (5) eicosenoic (2.1%) and (6) erucic (5.6%).

EXPERIMENTAL

Characteristics

For determination of characteristics standard text-books have been followed.

Consistency—White solid melting to a clear liquid with slightly yellowish colour having unpleasant smell and taste. M. p. 27°; Sp. gr. at 40°, 0.9021, S.E. 292.8; I.V. (Wij's), 73.4; R.M.V., 0.7; unsaponifiable matter, 0.7 (since S.V. × S.E. = 56,100. S.V. = 191.6).

Separation of Saturated and Unsaturated Fatty Acids

The fat (552 g.) was extracted with potassium carbonate solution in order to make it free from acids. The potassium soap after acidification gave free acids (57 g.) and the neutral fat remained (495 g.). In view of the small quantity of the free acids and possibility of decomposition of the acids involved no further investigation was undertaken. The acid-free fat (99 g.) was resolved into the following groups according to the method of Twitchell as modified by Hilditch (*loc. cit.*).

				Corresponding esters.		
				S.E.	I.V.	
Solid acids	40.4g.	41.9%	299.4	3.81
Liquid acids	56.0	58.1	293.4	136.80

The iodine values show that the separation of saturated from the unsaturated fatty acids is quite satisfactory.

Fractionation of Methyl Esters.—The methyl esters of solid acids (36.8 g.) and those of liquid acids (50.5 g.) were prepared as usual, of which 31.8 g. and 49.2 g. were taken separately for systematic fractionation through 'E.H.P. column' as described by Hilditch. The tables below summarise the complete fractionation data for the component acids of this fat. The composition of each ester fraction has been calculated from its S.E., I.V. and weight.

Fractional distillation of methyl esters of solid acids.
(31.75 g. distilled through "E.H.P. column")
Pressure during distillation maintained between 0.1–2 mm.

No.	Oil-bath.	Temperature of		Calculated composition of ester fractions.									
		Column		S.E.	I.V.	Saturated					Unsaturated		
		Middle	Head.			C ₁₆	C ₁₈	C ₂₀	C ₂₂	C ₂₄	E ₁₈ (OI)	N S	
S1	3.27g. 185-190°	152-158°	118-120°	271.6	1.0	3.06	0.17	—	—	—	—	0.04	—
S2	3.70 190°	158°	120-122°	270.6	0.7	3.61	0.06	—	—	—	—	0.03	—
S3	3.75 192°	156°	121°	270.4	1.1	3.69	0.01	—	—	—	—	0.05	—
S4	3.84 195°	156°	121 118°	270.3	1.4	3.78	—	—	—	—	—	0.06	—
S5	3.42 195-200°	156-170°	118° falling	272.9	6.7	3.15	—	—	—	—	—	0.27	—
S6	4.29 200-225°	170-200°	165°	324.2	9.5	—	—	3.51	0.30	—	—	0.48	—
S7	3.44 225-260°	200°	165° falling	352.2	1.7	—	—	0.05	3.32	—	—	0.07	—
S8	5.50 Residue	Residue	Residue	411.8	5.3	—	—	—	—	—	5.12	—	0.38
31.21				Wt.	17.29	0.24	3.56	3.62	5.12	1.00	—	0.38	—
				% Esters	55.4	0.8	11.4	11.6	16.4	3.2	—	1.2	—
				% Acids	55.8	0.8	11.6	11.8	16.8	3.2	—	—	—

* S₈ Esters freed from unsaponifiable matter ("N-S"), S.E. 383.8, I.V., 0.1.

Fractional distillation of methyl esters of the liquid acids.
(49.22 g. distilled through "E.H.P. column")
Pressure during distillation maintained between 0.1–2 mm.

No.	Oil-bath.	Temperature of		Calculated composition of ester fractions.								
		Column		S.E.	I.V.	Unsaturated						
		Middle.	Head.			C ₁₆	C ₁₈ (OI)	C ₁₈ (Li)	C ₂₀	C ₂₂	N-S	
L1	3.41g. 220°	210°	110-124°	276.5	99.5	2.27	0.84	0.30	—	—	—	—
L2	3.45 220°	205°	124°	285.8	126.7	1.08	0.86	1.51	—	—	—	—
L3	4.21 220-223°	206°	124°	288.4	144.8	0.88	0.56	2.77	—	—	—	—
L4	5.22 223°	206°	124-125°	290.2	150.3	0.75	0.67	3.80	—	—	—	—
L5	6.04 223°	206-207°	125°	290.4	148.9	0.84	0.89	4.31	—	—	—	—
L6	6.67 223-235°	207°	124-125°	289.7	148.8	1.08	0.87	4.72	—	—	—	—
L7	10.33 235-247°	207-210°	125-129°	286.5	146.7	2.83	0.54	6.96	—	—	—	—
L8	3.37 247-249°	215°	129-130°	302.7	129.9	—	0.57	1.80	1.00	—	—	—
L9	5.78 Residue	Residue	Residue	358.4	99.5	—	—	0.12	0.80	4.66	0.20	—
48.48				Wt.	9.73	5.80	26.29	1.80	4.66	0.20	—	—
				% Esters	20.1	12.0	54.2	3.7	9.6	0.4	—	—
				% Acids	20.0	12.0	54.5	3.8	9.7	—	—	—

* L₉ Esters freed from unsaponifiable matter ("N-S"), S.E. 346.2, I.V. 75.2.

Identification of Fatty Acids (Arachidic and Behenic acids).—The solutions left over after determination of S.E. of the fractions S₆ and S₇ were acidified and the solids so obtained were separately crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). Crystals from S₆, melting at 75° when compared with an authentic sample of arachidic acid show no depression of m.p. Similarly the crystals from S₇ melt at 82°. An authentic sample of behenic acid could not be obtained and its comparison therefore could not be undertaken.

Linoleic Acid.—A part of the liquid acids was brominated when a crystalline tetrabromo-stearic acid was obtained, m. p. 114°.

Various practical difficulties intervened in isolation and recognition of other fatty acids. So far as palmitic, oleic etc. are concerned their isolation and recognition are not of special importance since they have been reported in practically every instance so far encountered. Similarly, palmitoleic acid is now known to be a constituent of nearly all natural fats but in vegetable kingdom it is known to be a subordinate component. Its isolation is therefore important so far as the present work is concerned. Unfortunately, however, we have not had enough material to undertake this aspect of the question. This aspect of the question along with the glyceride structure of the fat will form a separate communication when sufficient material is obtained.

Acids. Saturated :	Calculated Composition of Fatty Acids			% Fatty acids	
		"Solid" acids S (41.9%).	"Liquid" acids L (58.1%).	Total.	(including unsaponifiable).
				(Wt.).	(Mol.).
<i>n</i> -Hexadecanoic, Palmitic (C ₁₆)	23.21	—	23.21	23.2	25.8
<i>n</i> -Octadecanoic, Stearic (C ₁₈)	0.32	—	0.32	0.3	0.3
<i>n</i> -Eicosenoic, Arachidic (C ₂₀)	4.78	—	4.78	4.8	4.3
<i>n</i> -Docosenoic, Behenic (C ₂₂)	4.86	—	2.86	4.9	4.1
<i>n</i> -Tetracosenoic, Lignoceric (C ₂₄)	6.88	—	6.88	6.9	5.3
Unsaturated :					
Δ ⁹ : ¹⁰ -Hexadecenoic, Palmitoleic (C ₁₆)	—	11.66	11.66	11.7	13.1
Δ ⁹ : ¹⁰ -Octadecenoic, Oleic (C ₁₈)	1.34	6.95	8.29	8.3	8.4
Δ ⁹ : ¹⁰ , ¹² : ¹³ -Octadecadienoic, Linoleic (C ₁₈)	—	31.52	31.52	31.5	32.0
Eicosenoic (probably Δ ¹¹ : ¹²) (C ₂₀)	—	2.15	2.15	2.1	2.0
Docosenoic (probably Δ ¹³ : ¹⁴), Erucic (C ₂₂)	—	5.58	5.58	5.6	4.7
Unsaponifiable	—	0.51	0.24	0.75	0.7

The fat is extremely rich in palmitic, palmitoleic and linoleic acids. The most interesting feature of this fat is the presence of so high a proportion of palmitoleic acid (11.7%), which has hitherto been known as a very subordinate component in land flora. It cannot be classed as a semi-drying oil in spite of linoleic acid content of 31.5%, since the iodine value on the whole fat is only 73.4. It must be classed as a non-drying oil and the best use that can be suggested for it is not as a direct soap-making material but as a diluent in the various oils and fats used in soap manufacture since the soap that will be formed by the mixed fatty acids of the oil is likely to be hard.

The author has experienced a great deal of difficulties while performing these experiments specially for the want of a suitable 'Hyvac' pump during ester fractionation and a Tesla Coil for determining the order of the vacuum. He wishes to express his thanks to the Principal of the College for giving him all facilities as far as possible under the existing circumstances and further to Prof. S. N. Bose of the University of Dacca for valuable help and guidance in calculating the ester fraction data.